

4onse: analysis of Four times Open Non-conventional system for Sensing the Environment

Calibration and testing report

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	RE	Restricted to a group specified by the project (including R4D services)	
	CO	Confidential, only for project and the R4D services	
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Change log

Version ¹	Date	Amended by	Changes
0.1	03-05-2018	D. Strigaro	Create document and prepared manuscript
1.0	28-10-2019	D. Strigaro	Update content with articles published in Sensors MDPI
1.1			

Partners involved in the work execution

Versions	Partner Name	People involved
0.1	SUPSI	D. Strigaro, M. Cannata
1.0	SUPSI	D. Strigaro, M. Cannata
1.1		

NOTES:

For comments / suggestions / contributions to this document, contact the Coordinator of 4onse project at massimiliano.cannata@supsi.ch

For more information on the project 4onse, link to <http://www.4onse.ch>

¹ Please start with version number 0.1. Any further minor review will increase the version number by 0.1 while a major review will increase the version by 1.0.

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Executive summary

A 4onse weather station prototype was installed nearby a conventional weather station of the Hydro-meteorological network of the Canton Ticino in Switzerland. The data time-series collected by the two stations during a period of 6 months were compared and evaluated in terms of data accuracy and goodness-of-fit.

The results of this activity were published into the Sensors journal of the MDPI with an Impact Factor (IF) of 3.031 (2018). The publication is open access and available on-line [1] or in attached annex (A01).

Reference

[1] Strigaro, D.; Cannata, M.; Antonovic, M. Boosting a Weather Monitoring System in Low Income Economies Using Open and Non-Conventional Systems: Data Quality Analysis. Sensors 2019, 19, 1185. <https://www.mdpi.com/424220>